

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D9.5 Exploitation activities roadmap

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Glossary and Abbreviations

ASSB	All Solid-State Batteries
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KTA	Key Technological Areas
Gen 4b SSB	generation 4b solid state battery
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
R&D	Research and Development
SSB	Solid-State Batteries
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TP	Technological Pillars

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Executive Summary

The aim of SPINMATE is to demonstrate a digitally driven proof-of-concept pilot line that is scalable, sustainable, safe, and cost effective as a first step toward the large-scale production of generation 4b solid state battery (Gen 4b SSB) cells and modules to support the electrification of the automotive industry.

SPINMATE processing and manufacturing innovations will contribute for:

- a sustainable and competitive large-scale production of SSBs,
- the reduction of the carbon footprint,
- enhancement of safety along the entire value chain,
- and SSB-based technologies development to achieve a mass electrification of the automotive sector.

This report includes in Chapter 2 a market analysis for SSB manufacturing, describing how this market is positioned, particularly in Europe, analysing the different target market segments and take a look to the future on the expected impact of SSB adoption. Furthermore, a more detailed analysis on the SSB market made in Chapter 3 on SSB key players and a PESTLE analysis to have a perspective on the importance given in Europe to have the ambition to position the continent as a leader in sustainable mobility. Finally, the last two chapters set the exploitation strategy of SPINMATE. Chapter 4 describes the concept behind the motive and importance of preparing exploitation activities in the project. In Chapter 5, the exploitation roadmap is presented, listing the activities prepared to involve all SPINMATE partners in setting their exploitation scenarios for each of the Key Exploitable Results (KER) identified for SPINMATE. The goal of preparing these activities will be to define new Business Models for SPINMATE results, ensuring the legacy of innovative practices and continuous improvement of Solid-State Batteries field.

1. Introduction

The exploitation of the project's results has a crucial role to determine the success of SPINMATE. The exploitation strategy of the project is sought to contribute significantly to one of the project objectives:

- *SO6: To create and establish a wide knowledge portfolio, engaging the key stakeholders and end users to expand the project's scope towards new market opportunities to maximise its impact.*

The aim of this document is to design an exploitation strategy to help each partner define the routes for making the results available for use by other parties after the termination of the project. For this purpose, it is worth highlighting the definition of exploitation. Exploitation is the use of results that have been selected and prioritised due to their high potential to be used (in activities other than those covered by the action) and derive benefits-downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research, or education. Results used for developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

The Key Exploitable Results (KER) for SPINMATE have been identified and categorised under its three main technological pillars: i) Development, Optimisation and Upscaling of SSB Cell Components, ii) Digitalisation and modelling for SSB cell manufacturing, and iii) Pilot line optimisation and demonstration.

This report is the exploitation activities roadmap which will aim to develop and assess the potential exploitation activities after the project ends, including:

1. Target groups and sector of application: The audience to whom the results are being made available to, and the sector interested in such results.
2. Quantitative targets and indicators: These are measurable goals to be achieved from a partner level to manage the successful exploitation.
3. Impact: The economic, commercial, societal, environmental, technical, educational, or scientific effect each result will cause.
4. IPR measures: The specification of the ownership for each innovation, including after the end of the project. For example, patents, copyright, or trademarks available in place, or non-relevancy.
5. Possible risks and barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures: These are foreseeable impediments for exploiting the results and the strategy in place to counterbalance them.
6. Development of Business Models to define exploitation plans for the SPINMATE KER.

2. Market Analysis

The European Commission (EC) is fully committed to tackling one of the most pressing challenges of our time: climate change. To achieve a climate-neutral Europe by 2050, the EC has proposed numerous initiatives and reforms. Among these, the development and deployment of advanced battery technologies are critical in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which are the primary drivers of global warming. Batteries are essential for energy storage across various sectors, including transportation, power, and industry.

The demand for batteries in Europe is rapidly increasing, with forecasts predicting it will almost reach 400 GWh in 2025 and expected to reach 1,600 GWh in 2040¹. This surge is primarily driven by the electric vehicle (EV) market, which held a 4.5% market share in Europe in 2019. Recognizing the significance of EVs in reducing GHG emissions, the EC has identified the EV sector as crucial for achieving zero CO₂ emissions from new vehicles sold by 2035.

Currently, the battery market in Europe is dominated by Lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries², which have seen significant improvements in energy density and cost reductions—energy density has more than doubled, and costs have decreased by a factor of ten. However, conventional Li-ion batteries are nearing their performance limits and face safety concerns. Therefore, the development of next-generation batteries, such as Solid-State Batteries (SSBs), is essential for establishing a new industry value chain in Europe and advancing their commercialization³.

High-energy-density, EU-manufactured SSBs will be crucial in ensuring a stable supply for various sectors, particularly the automotive industry. Achieving this will require the advancement and deployment of innovative manufacturing technologies capable of large-scale SSB production. The BATTERY 2030+ roadmap highlights manufacturability as a key area for the development and production of sustainable batteries. Advanced and scalable manufacturing techniques for SSBs are expected to drive cost reductions, improve energy efficiency, and enhance safety.

2.1 SSB Market Today

The electric vehicle market in Europe is experiencing rapid growth due to increased environmental awareness, government incentives, and technological advancements. European EV sales reached approximately 1.4 million units in 2020, with projections indicating significant growth in the coming years. Europe accounted for 25% of global electric car sales in 2023 and is projected to maintain this share in 2024, continuing to be the second largest market for electric vehicles after China⁴. This growth is fuelling the demand for batteries, particularly those offering higher energy densities and improved safety features.

¹ European Commission – Lithium-based batteries supply chain challenges - <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/analysis-of-supply-chain-challenges-49b749>

² Journal of Industry Ecology, Volume27, Issue3 June 2023, Pages 964-976 - Lithium-ion battery cell production in Europe: Scenarios for reducing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions until 2030 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13386>

³ Advancements and challenges in solid-state lithium-ion batteries: From ion conductors to industrialization - <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2214785324003663>

⁴ Virta – The Global Electric Vehicle market overview in 2024 <https://www.virta.global/global-electric-vehicle-market>

Solid-State Batteries (SSBs) represent a promising advancement over traditional Li-ion batteries⁵. SSBs use a solid electrolyte instead of a liquid one, which can provide higher energy density, longer life cycles, and enhanced safety. The European market for SSBs is anticipated to grow substantially, with investments and research driving the development of commercially viable SSBs. By 2030, Europe aims to become a leader in SSB production, supporting its transition to sustainable and efficient energy storage solutions.

SSBs are considered a crucial advancement in the roadmaps of all original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) due to their potential to significantly enhance the performance of EV. When applying SSBs, the driving distance of EV can be doubled, due to their higher energy density compared to traditional lithium-ion batteries. This increased energy density means that vehicles can travel longer distances on a single charge, addressing one of the major concerns of range anxiety among consumers. Furthermore, SSBs offer improved intrinsic safety features, reducing the risk of battery fires and improving overall vehicle safety. Despite these advantages, SSBs still face challenges such as lower cyclic performance, which affects the battery's longevity and efficiency over multiple charge and discharge cycles⁶. Additionally, they suffer from high interface resistance, particularly on the cathode side, which impedes their overall performance and efficiency. To overcome these hurdles, ongoing research and development in Advanced Materials focus on pushing SSB technology beyond the current state-of-the-art, aiming to maximise performance and reliability for future EV. This includes innovations in materials, manufacturing processes, and battery design to fully recognise the potential of SSBs in the automotive industry.⁷

Figure 1 presents a comparison between SSBs and Traditional Batteries⁸.

Figure 1 – Solid-State Batteries vs Traditional Batteries (Source: UNDP)

⁵ Kazyak, E., García-Méndez, R. Recent progress and challenges for manufacturing and operating solid-state batteries for electric vehicles. MRS Bulletin 49, 717-729 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43577-024-00740-7>

⁶ Janek, J., Zeier, W.G. Challenges in speeding up solid-state battery development. Nat Energy 8, 230-240 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01208-9>

⁷ European Commission – [Roadmap on Advanced Materials for Batteries. Prepared by Working Group 3](#)

⁸ UNDP – [Solid-State Batteries vs Traditional Batteries](#)

Europe is heavily investing in the research and development (R&D) of SSBs, with numerous initiatives supported by both public and private sectors. Leading automotive manufacturers, battery producers, and research institutions are collaborating to advance SSB technology. Key projects include:

- **Battery 2030+ Initiative:** This EU-funded initiative focuses on long-term research to create high-performance, safe, and sustainable batteries.
- **European Battery Alliance (EBA):** The EBA aims to create a competitive and sustainable battery cell manufacturing value chain in Europe. It supports various R&D projects related to SSBs.

European governments and the European Union are providing substantial support through funding and policy measures to foster the development of SSBs:

- **Horizon Europe:** The EU's research and innovation framework program includes significant funding for battery technologies, including SSBs.
- **Regulatory Framework:** Policies aimed at reducing carbon emissions and promoting clean energy are creating a favourable environment for SSB adoption. For example, the EU's CO₂ emission standards for vehicles are driving the demand for more efficient battery technologies like SSBs.

2.2 Target market segments

The key target market sectors for the electrification of the automotive sector and the global GHG emissions reduction from electric vehicles in Europe, considering the sustainable and competitive large-scale production of SSB, reduction of the carbon footprint, and enhancement of safety along the entire value chain, include:

Automotive Manufacturing

Sustainable and Competitive Large-Scale Production

Electric Vehicles (EVs): The European automotive industry, including major players like Volkswagen, BMW, Renault, and Toyota Europe, is at the forefront of integrating SSBs into electric vehicles. These manufacturers are focused on improving vehicle range, reducing charging times, and enhancing performance to maintain competitiveness and adhere to EU regulations.

European Battery Alliance (EBA): Initiatives like the EBA are crucial for fostering collaboration between automakers, suppliers, and research institutions to develop and scale up SSB production across Europe.

Reduction of Carbon Footprint

Supply Chain Optimization: European automakers are optimizing their supply chains to reduce the carbon footprint by incorporating renewable energy sources in production facilities and enhancing recycling initiatives for battery materials.

EU Emission Standards: Compliance with stringent EU CO₂ emission standards drives the adoption of SSBs, helping to lower the overall lifecycle emissions of vehicles.

Enhancement of Safety

Battery Safety: European automotive manufacturers prioritize the safety advantages of SSBs, including reduced thermal runaway and fire hazards, enhancing the safety of EVs for both users and first responders.

Regulatory Compliance: Adhering to EU safety regulations, SSBs help automakers meet high safety standards, providing a safer transportation ecosystem.

Energy and Utilities

Sustainable and Competitive Large-Scale Production

Grid Storage Solutions: European energy companies are leveraging SSB technology for grid storage solutions, crucial for integrating renewable energy sources and ensuring grid stability. Initiatives such as Horizon Europe support research in this area.

Renewable Energy Integration: SSBs facilitate the storage of energy from renewable sources like wind and solar, contributing to Europe's sustainable energy infrastructure.

Reduction of Carbon Footprint

Clean Energy Storage: Storing energy from renewable sources with SSBs helps reduce reliance on fossil fuels and lowers the overall carbon footprint of Europe's energy sector.

Efficiency Improvements: SSBs improve energy storage efficiency, reducing waste and enhancing the sustainability of energy systems across Europe.

Enhancement of Safety

Infrastructure Safety: Deploying SSBs in energy storage systems enhances the safety of the energy infrastructure, mitigating risks associated with traditional battery storage solutions.

Operational Safety: SSBs provide safer operating environments for energy storage facilities, reducing risks of leaks and explosions.

Consumer Electronics and Portable Devices

Sustainable and Competitive Large-Scale Production

High-Performance Devices: European companies like Siemens and Bosch are integrating SSBs into high-performance consumer electronics such as smartphones, laptops, and wearables, aiming for longer battery life and faster charging capabilities.

Innovation and Market Demand: The European consumer electronics market drives demand for advanced battery technologies like SSBs, meeting performance expectations while supporting sustainability goals.

Reduction of Carbon Footprint

Eco-Friendly Products: European manufacturers are focusing on creating eco-friendly consumer electronics with lower carbon footprints, supported by the integration of energy-efficient SSBs.

Recycling Programs: Implementing robust recycling programs for SSBs in consumer electronics helps reduce environmental impact and carbon footprint across Europe.

Enhancement of Safety

Product Safety: SSBs enhance the safety of consumer electronics by reducing risks of overheating and fires, which is particularly important for portable devices used daily by European consumers.

User Confidence: Improved safety features in consumer electronics boost user confidence and satisfaction, driving market growth in Europe.

The key target market sectors for the electrification of the automotive sector and global GHG emissions reduction from electric vehicles in Europe include automotive manufacturing, energy and utilities, and consumer electronics. These sectors benefit from the sustainable and competitive large-scale production of SSBs, reduction of the carbon footprint, and enhancement of safety across the value chain. European policymakers and key players such as the European Commission, the European Battery Alliance, and major European corporations are actively supporting these developments to achieve climate goals, improve safety standards, and foster innovation in energy storage and utilization.

2.3 Expected Impact

Approximately 70% of a battery cell's cost is attributed to the cathode, anode, separator, and electrolyte materials, making advanced materials crucial for cost reduction and market adoption. Ongoing research and innovation (R&I) in these materials aim to develop more cost-efficient, high-performing, safer, and sustainable battery cells. The primary goal of R&I in battery materials is to increase the energy density of cells, enhancing their performance and cost-competitiveness for various applications.

Different battery chemistries are being developed to cater to specific applications beyond mobility and stationary usage. In mobility, the focus is on liquid-state batteries (generation 3) with advancements towards solid-state batteries (generation 4), while research also explores generation 5 chemistries. For stationary storage, alongside Li-ion batteries, there are developments in Na-ion, redox-flow, and metal-air batteries. Further R&I is needed to develop suitable advanced materials for these chemistries.

By 2030, Li-ion technologies are expected to dominate mobility applications due to their successful market uptake, established industrial value chain, and continuous improvements. The main R&I focus will be on enhancing energy density and other key performance indicators. Solid-state batteries (generation 4) and generation 5 chemistries will also receive significant attention, potentially making progress in specific application segments. For stationary usage, a broader range of technologies will be available. Beyond 2030, new chemistries are anticipated to emerge⁹.

The expected impacts are as follows:

- Technological Impact:
 - o SSBs are anticipated to emerge as the most promising technology for use in EVs over the next several decades. SSBs are expected to revolutionize the EV market by offering significantly higher energy densities, improved safety features, and longer lifespans compared to current lithium-ion batteries. This technological

⁹ Batteries Europe – [Powering Europe's Green Revolution: Paving the Way to a More Resilient and Sustainable Battery Industry](#)

leap will support the advancement of EV performance, making them more appealing to consumers and accelerating the transition to electric mobility.

- Economic Impact:
 - The share of advanced materials in the battery cell cost structure is substantial, making innovation in advanced materials for solid-state batteries a critical driver of economic growth. This innovation is crucial for maintaining and enhancing European competitiveness in the global market. The development and integration of these advanced materials will be a cornerstone for the future of Europe's Giga Factories, which are large-scale battery manufacturing facilities. These Giga Factories will not only boost the regional economy but also create numerous jobs and position Europe as a leader in battery technology production.
- Environmental Impact:
 - The advancements in solid-state battery technology will facilitate a carbon-neutral and circular approach to mobility. This means that the entire lifecycle of batteries, from production to disposal, will be designed to minimise environmental impact. Developments will include comprehensive life cycle analyses to understand and mitigate the environmental footprint of battery production. Additionally, emphasis will be placed on the reuse and recycling of battery materials, ensuring that the resources used in battery production can be recovered and repurposed, thereby reducing waste and conserving natural resources. This circular economy approach will play a vital role in achieving sustainability goals and reducing the overall carbon footprint of the mobility sector¹.

3. SSB market

3.1 Key players

The EV market is undergoing significant transformation, driven by advancements in battery technology, particularly SSBs. SSBs offer higher energy density, improved safety, and longer life cycles compared to traditional lithium-ion batteries. The following analysis focuses on the major players in the EV market incorporating SSB technology, their specific technologies, and their market share.

Figure 2 – Global Solid-State Battery Global Market (TrendForce)

All-solid-state batteries (ASSBs) face several technical challenges that have prevented large-scale production, including issues with electrolyte material preparation, interface stability, and cell production processes. Despite these obstacles, significant global investment and attention, particularly from Japan, South Korea, Europe, and the US, have led to substantial progress, with expectations for mass production within the next 3-5 years.

ASSBs are a critical focus in the race for next-generation battery technology and have been integrated into national development strategies by major regions, including the European Union. ASSBs can be categorized into four types based on solid electrolyte materials: polymer, oxide, halide, and sulfide, each with distinct advantages and drawbacks. Japan and South Korea primarily focus on sulfide-based ASSBs.

Japan, an early leader in ASSB R&D, holds the most patents in this field, with companies like Toyota and Nissan aiming for mass production around 2028. In South Korea, major manufacturers such as Samsung SDI, SK Innovation, and LG Energy Solutions are heavily investing in R&D. Samsung SDI completed a pilot production line in 2023, targeting mass production by 2027.

In the United States, ASSB development is driven by innovative startups like QuantumScape and Solid Power, which have products in advanced prototype stages. Companies like SES, Ampcera, Factorial Energy, 24M Technologies, and Ionic Materials are also making significant strides in solid-state battery technology¹⁰.

Although China currently leads as the world's largest manufacturer of lithium-ion batteries (LiBs), it lags behind international competitors regarding the patent landscape for all-solid-state batteries (ASSBs). European research and development efforts have highlighted this gap, emphasizing the advanced positions of other global players. China's solid-state battery technology strategy is diverse, focusing mainly on semi-solid and state-liquid hybrids. Semi-solid-state batteries have achieved small-scale production and are being adopted in vehicles. However, investment in ASSB technology in China remains insufficient, with resources dispersed across various projects, leading to a significant difference compared to international leaders.

European countries, particularly Germany and France, have been at the forefront of ASSB research and innovation. European efforts are concentrated on achieving higher energy densities and enhanced safety features through solid-state technology. This includes initiatives like the European Battery Alliance, which aims to foster collaboration across the continent to advance battery technologies and establish a competitive battery manufacturing ecosystem in Europe¹¹. Furthermore, the European Union has been investing heavily in research and innovation through the Horizon Europe programme, targeting advancements in ASSB technology.

Blue Solutions¹², a French company, has emerged as a key player in the solid-state battery market, notably by integrating these advanced batteries into their vehicles. Renowned for their pioneering technology, Blue Solutions offers electric cars that utilize solid-state batteries, which promise enhanced safety, higher energy density, and longer life spans compared to traditional lithium-ion batteries. Despite these advantages, the primary drawback of Blue Solutions' solid-state batteries is their operational temperature requirement; they only function effectively at temperatures above 60-80°C. This high-temperature dependency poses a significant challenge for widespread adoption, as it necessitates additional heating systems to maintain the required operational temperature, potentially impacting overall efficiency and cost.

Given these concerted efforts, European companies, along with those from Japan, South Korea, and the United States, are well-positioned to surpass China in the ASSB domain. This potential shift is poised to reshape the competitive landscape of the future electric vehicle (EV) battery industry, leveraging Europe's strong foundation in advanced materials research and collaborative innovation networks¹³.

¹⁰ TrendForce – [\[Insights\] China's Position in EV Battery Market to be Shaken as the Mass Production Race of All-Solid-State Battery Industry Speeds up?](#)

¹¹ EC – [European Battery Alliance](#)

¹² Blue Solutions [website](#)

¹³ EC – [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for Batteries 2020](#)

3.2 SSB PESTLE Analysis through the eyes of EU

PESTLE analysis¹⁴ is a strategic tool that evaluates six key external factors affecting a market: Political (government policies and regulations), Economic (economic conditions like growth and inflation), Social (demographics and cultural trends), Technological (innovation and technology adoption), Legal (laws and regulations), and Environmental (sustainability and climate impact) below is described how SSB market is operated in Europe.

Political: EC has prioritised the development and commercialisation of solid-state batteries (SSBs) as central to its strategy for reducing GHG emissions. Initiatives such as the European Green Deal and the Fit for 55¹⁵ package aim to cut emissions by at least 55% by 2030 and achieve climate neutrality by 2050. These policies highlight the essential role of advanced battery technologies in achieving these targets. The European Battery Alliance and the Strategic Action Plan on Batteries are crucial in providing regulatory incentives and substantial funding to stimulate innovation and market adoption of SSBs, ensuring Europe remains competitive globally¹⁶.

Economic: The EC's Horizon Europe programme is a major financial pillar supporting the development of advanced battery technologies, including SSBs. Significant investment in SSBs is crucial for maintaining Europe's competitive edge in the global battery market. The increasing demand for electric vehicles (EVs), driven by consumer preferences for sustainable options and government incentives, ensures a robust market for cost-effective and high-performance SSBs. This market-oriented approach is essential for fostering a resilient and self-sufficient battery industry within Europe, creating economic growth and job opportunities¹⁷.

Social: Consumer demand for environmentally sustainable products is rising across Europe, driving the market for EVs powered by SSBs. This transition promises significant reductions in air pollution, thereby improving public health. Additionally, establishing a new SSB value chain is expected to generate many jobs in research, manufacturing, and related services, promoting social stability and economic development. These advancements are aligned with the EU's broader objectives for sustainable growth and societal well-being, further supporting market acceptance and consumer trust in new technologies.

Technological: Europe leads in technological advancements within the battery sector, focusing on overcoming the key challenges of SSBs, such as enhancing electrolyte stability and interface dynamics. Programmes like Horizon Europe continue to provide substantial funding and foster international collaborations aimed at driving technological breakthroughs in battery innovation. These efforts are critical for scaling up production and ensuring Europe's leadership in the global battery industry. A market-oriented approach that emphasises innovation and practical application will ensure the rapid commercialisation of these technologies.

Legal: The commercialisation of SSBs in Europe is supported by strict safety and environmental regulations that ensure high performance and sustainability standards. The EC's regulatory framework also supports robust intellectual property protection, encouraging continuous investment in R&D. Additionally, recent updates in international trade agreements enhance the availability of raw materials and expand market opportunities for European SSB manufacturers,

¹⁴ CIPD – [Pestle Analysis](#)

¹⁵ EC – [Timeline - European Green Deal and Fit for 55](#)

¹⁶ The European Green Deal - [Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent](#)

¹⁷ European Union – [EU energy policy](#)

promoting a more competitive industry. A well-regulated market environment ensures investor confidence and industry stability.

Environmental: The development and adoption of SSBs are integral to Europe’s environmental goals, as outlined in the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Promoting SSBs can significantly reduce GHG emissions from the automotive sector, contributing to a projected 16% reduction in global emissions by 2035. Furthermore, the emphasis on sustainable production practices and recycling initiatives ensures that the environmental impact of battery manufacturing is minimised, supporting a circular economy and long-term ecological sustainability. This aligns with the market demand for greener technologies and sustainable practices¹⁸.

¹⁸ IEA – [Global EV Outlook 2020](#)

4. Framework

The purpose of the Exploitation Framework is to establish a common understanding of concepts related to innovation, exploitation, dissemination and communication, and to support the planning and implementation of exploitation activities in SPINMATE. The framework is established to promote the following tasks:

- Defining the focus of exploitation and setting priorities. The project has identified multiple results that are potentially exploitable.
- Connecting the exploitation work with other activities in which SPINMATE can contribute with valuable input for modelling exploitation plans.
- Identifying gaps in the work and in the process and addressing those to filling these gaps.

The following image illustrates the key steps taken in the project to feed three key activities in SPINMATE – Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation to assess the project key exploitable results for the preparation of new business models.

Figure 3 – Activities preceding KER

To assess the importance and meaning of SPINMATE Key Exploitable Results, it must consider the following aspects:

- **SPINMATE Innovation Management** is part of the overall project management, assessing the TRL upscale on the overall work packages including the monitor of stakeholders' needs relevant to the project and the technological developments related to these needs. The identification of technological gaps and market needs will provide advice to the project for prioritizing and developing exploitation strategies, while assessing IPR issues on the individual interest of exploitation from SPINMATE partners.
- **Exploitation:** Exploitation involves using project results, encompassing both commercial and non-commercial uses. This includes applications in further research, public policymaking, or other relevant fields.
- **Dissemination:** Dissemination focuses on describing the results and ensuring their availability for use. It supports exploitation by targeting specific audiences as defined by the exploitation strategy. Depending on the type of results and the strategy,

dissemination may reach various users, such as peers in the research field, industry professionals, other commercial players, and policymakers.

- **Communication:** Communication involves informing and promoting the project and its results, as well as collecting feedback. The goal is to create awareness and target a broader audience, thereby attracting potential adopters of the project's outcomes.

5. Exploitation roadmap

This chapter describes the strategy for the exploitation activities of SPINMATE. To assess how the partners will identify, classify, measure, and plan their exploitation strategy on the results that will be achieved during the project, INOVA has defined a group of activities presented in the diagram below.

Figure 4 – SPINMATE exploitation roadmap

In Phase 1, INOVA will distribute a survey to SPINMATE partners to collect their individual interests for the exploitation of project KERs. The survey has been designed and is included in Annex 1.

In Phase 2, INOVA will establish End-Users Group to foster discussion on potential joint exploitation of KER. SPINMATE partners can occupy a different position in the SSB value chain. The goal will be to get different impressions and inputs according to the expertise and know-how on the respective market in different value chain positions.

An overview of the SSB value chain to be considered in SPINMATE is illustrated below.

Figure 5 – SSB value chain

In Phase 3, INOVA will create a Workshop to foster discussion on exploitation strategies and business opportunities between SPINMATE partners to jointly explore the results of the project, while assessing potential IPR issues.

At the end, new business models will be developed based on the project's results. These business models can be created individually by partners who do not wish to share their exploitation plans. In other cases, for Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that involve two or more SPINMATE partners, collaborative business models will be prepared.

The SPINMATE Business Models will have the following areas which will be considered during each phase of the SPINMATE exploitation roadmap.

Economic and Social Impact

- Job creation and economic benefits.
- Impact on related industries and supply chains.
- Long-term economic outlook.
- Support for regional development and cohesion.

Sustainability and Environmental Impact

- Lifecycle analysis of batteries.
- Environmental benefits and challenges.
- Recycling and end-of-life management.
- Contribution to EU's circular economy and climate neutrality goals.

Monitoring and Evaluation

- Key performance indicators (KPIs) for progress tracking.
- Feedback mechanisms and continuous improvement strategies.
- Post-launch evaluation and market feedback.
- Compliance with EU sustainability reporting standards.

Communication and Dissemination

- Stakeholder communication plan.
- Marketing and outreach strategies.
- Public relations and media engagement.
- Promotion of sustainability achievements and contributions to EU goals.

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- ² Journal of Industry Ecology, Volume27, Issue3 June 2023, Pages 964-976 - Lithium-ion battery cell production in Europe: Scenarios for reducing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions until 2030 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13386>
- ³ Advancements and challenges in solid-state lithium-ion batteries: From ion conductors to industrialization - <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2214785324003663>
- ⁴ Virta – The Global Electric Vehicle market overview in 2024 <https://www.virta.global/global-electric-vehicle-market>
- ⁵ Kazyak, E., García-Méndez, R. Recent progress and challenges for manufacturing and operating solid-state batteries for electric vehicles. MRS Bulletin 49, 717-729 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43577-024-00740-7>
- ⁶ Janek, J., Zeier, W.G. Challenges in speeding up solid-state battery development. Nat Energy 8, 230-240 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01208-9>
- ⁷ European Commission – [Roadmap on Advanced Materials for Batteries. Prepared by Working Group 3](#)
- ⁸ UNDP – [Solid-State Batteries vs Traditional Batteries](#)
- ⁹ Batteries Europe – [Powering Europe's Green Revolution: Paving the Way to a More Resilient and Sustainable Battery Industry](#)
- ¹⁰ TrendForce – [\[Insights\] China's Position in EV Battery Market to be Shaken as the Mass Production Race of All-Solid-State Battery Industry Speeds up?](#)
- ¹¹ EC – [European Battery Alliance](#)
- ¹² Blue Solutions [website](#)
- ¹³ EC – [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for Batteries 2020](#)
- ¹⁴ CIPD – [Pestle Analysis](#)
- ¹⁵ EC – [Timeline - European Green Deal and Fit for 55](#)
- ¹⁶ The European Green Deal - [Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent](#)
- ¹⁷ European Union – [EU energy policy](#)
- ¹⁸ IEA – [Global EV Outlook 2020](#)

Annex 1 – Exploitation interests per Partner

[INFORMATION FROM SPINMATE D9.1]

The project results have a high business and innovation potential for the SPINMATE consortium and will be exploited through the exploitation strategy above-mentioned. Also, these results will serve as inputs for the first step – Identification – of the Exploitation strategy explained. Beyond the implementation phase, the SPINMATE’s consortium is committed to work on the following exploitation activities after the end of the project: industrial upscaling & technology refinement (from TRL6 to TRL8), development and implementation of the go-to-market/commercial plan, definition of specific products/services linked to the exploitable results, formalisation of business agreements, implementation of funding and investment plans to scale-up the results until a market uptake stage (TRL7), certification of future products/services and activation of IPR mechanisms linked to the exploitable results and keep alive FTO analysis. The Table below presents the exploitation interests from each partner in SPINMATE under the Technological Pillars (TP) of the project and their respective Key Technological Areas (KTA).

TP	Development, Optimisation And Upscaling Of SSB Cell Components		Digitalisation and modelling for ssb cell manufacturing		Pilot line optimisation and demonstration	
KTA	Solid Polymer Electrolyte	Li metal anode	Ni rich NMC based Cathode	Digitalisation approaches for the assembly and manufacturing at the pilot line level	Simulation of a digital-driven manufacturing environment: industrial upscaling	Proof-of-concept pilot line towards Gen 4b SSB cells manufacturing
P1: ABEE		<p>Equipment: Li-metal anode coater</p> <p>Processes: Li production, protective layer involvement on it, and integration in Gen4 SSB.</p> <p>Services: Internal use, further R&D, industrial contracts.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: trade secret and patent</p>				<p>Equipment: Assembly line for SSB.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Know-how on processing and manufacturing of small and large battery cells. Business Opportunity / IP Protection: New engineering services regarding smart, flexible and green manufacturing of next generation SSB cell technologies secured by trade secret.</p>
P2: ISCF						<p>Equipment: Assembly line in Glovebox.</p> <p>Processes: Mixing, coating and lamination processes for polymer SSB Systems.</p> <p>Products: Monolayer cells, tailored polymer compositions.</p> <p>Services: R&D Services.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Processing and manufacturing on</p>

						cell level. Broad polymer electrolyte know how and patents.
P3: COMAU				<p>Products: Models of all the process steps of gen4b cell manufacturing.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Knowhow about the correlations among process parameters, to provide a forecast of the final product quality and tools for rework strategy and predictive maintenance.</p>	<p>Products: Model of the whole production process, considering a large-scale (giga) environment.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Assessment of the efficiency of the developed manufacturing processes and equipment applied to an industrial scenario.</p>	<p>Equipment: Cutting tools for new electrode and separator materials; handling systems for stacking gen4b cells based on metallic lithium and polymeric / hybrid electrolyte.</p> <p>Processes: Products: Equipment for gen4b cell assembly.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Knowhow about handling of new electrode and electrolyte materials for gen4b cell assembly.</p>
P4: TUBS				<p>Processes: Modelling of process-structure-property relationships for the scalable production of polymer SSB cathodes.</p> <p>Products: Process models.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Knowhow about the correlation between processing and the resulting properties of polymer SSB cathodes.</p>		<p>Equipment: Small pilot line under dry room conditions.</p> <p>Processes: Mixing and dispersing, (extrusion), coating and drying, calendaring, cell assembly.</p> <p>Products: Mono- and multi-layer polymer solid-state battery cells.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP: Know-how on processing and manufacturing of small and large solid-state battery cells with polymer solid electrolyte via scalable methods.</p>
P5: TME	Other forms of knowledge (Publication of results on scientific and non-scientific magazines and on different media).					
P6: CEA						<p>Knowledge & IP: Improvement of SSB cells analysis, tests, and safety</p> <p>Use of new sensors for tests</p> <p>SSB material analysis with safe procedures.</p>
P7: CID	<p>Processes: SPE integration in Geb4 SSB.</p> <p>Services: Internal use, further R&D, industrial contracts.</p> <p>Knowledge & IP:</p>	<p>Processes: Li handling and integration in Gen4 SSB.</p> <p>Services: Internal use, further R&D, industrial</p>	<p>Processes: Conditions for SSB cathode production.</p> <p>Products: Cathode for SSB.</p> <p>Services: Internal</p>	<p>Processes: Manufacturing process of advanced SSB.</p> <p>Products: Advanced SSB.</p> <p>Services: Internal</p>		<p>Processes: Manufacturing process of advanced Gen4 SSB.</p> <p>Products: Advanced Gen4 SSB.</p> <p>Services: Internal</p>

	trade secret.	contracts. Knowledge & IP: trade secret.	use, further R&D, industrial contracts. <u>Knowledge & IP:</u> trade secret and patent.	use, licensing, and further R&D. <u>Knowledge & IP:</u> trade secret.		use, licensing, and further R&D. <u>Knowledge & IP:</u> trade secret and patent.
P8: CICE	<u>Processes:</u> Solvent-free processing of solid polymer electrolytes (with or without Garnet). <u>Products:</u> Polymer electrolyte with high ionic conductivity and electrochemical stability. <u>Knowledge & IP:</u> Patents, publications.		<u>Processes:</u> Cathode solvent-free processing; Integration of polymer electrolyte on cathode layer. <u>Products:</u> Extruded cathode. <u>Knowledge & IP:</u> Patents, publications.			
P9: ARKEMA	<u>Processes:</u> Solvent process to produce the electrolyte and catholyte; A solvent-free processing route for the electrolyte assembly, avoiding the use of toxic organic solvents and decrease the processing costs. <u>Products:</u> A novel solid polymer electrolyte, with high ionic conductivity (ca. 10 ⁻³ S cm ⁻¹ at room temperature) and a wide electrochemical stability (>4.4 V vs Li ⁺ /Li). <u>Knowledge & IP:</u> Freedom to operate or license.					
P10: INEGI						<u>Knowledge & IP:</u> Gain of knowledge regarding the main parameters and drivers for sustainable manufacturing of SSB to support relevant national stakeholders and industry. <u>Other:</u> Matured digital data platform tool for support in handling large datasets of life cycle inventories for sustainability assessments; Publication of

						results in scientific journals and national relevant media.
P11: IREC			<p><u>Processes:</u> Active material, electrolyte and additives processing conditions to optimize performance.</p> <p><u>Products:</u> Cathode for SSB.</p> <p><u>Services:</u> Internal use, further R&D, industrial contracts.</p> <p><u>Knowledge & IP:</u> Publications and patents.</p>			
P12: CPT			<p><u>Equipment:</u> optimize equipment and parameters for manufacturing of cathode materials.</p> <p><u>Processes:</u> Protocols for manufacturing of cathode materials.</p> <p><u>Products:</u> Ceramic oxide powders for cathode materials.</p> <p><u>Knowledge & IP:</u> FTP, Patents.</p>			
P13: INOVA+	Other forms of knowledge (Publication of results on scientific and non-scientific magazines and on different media).					

Annex 2 – SPINMATE Individual KER assessment Survey

KER Title
Lead Partner
TRL
Initial:
Current:
Expected to achieve by the end of SPINMATE:
Section 1 – KER Value
1.1 Description – write a short sentence to describe the KER, including (i) what it is, (ii) what are its key functions/features/characteristics.
1.2 State of the Art – What is the current State of the Art of this result.
1.3 Describe potential market barriers (external factors) for the buyers/final users for the exploitation of this result.
1.4 Which are the major competitors of your entity in particular to this KTE (National/European/International)?
1.5 How this result/KER distinguishes or complements what already exists in the market, including the identification of key benefits.
1.6 Which impact will cause, and explain where applicable, considering (i) Social; (ii) Environmental; (iii) Political; (iv) Scientific; (v) Technological.
1.7 Select the form(s) in which this KER can be used:
<input type="checkbox"/> Research Roadmaps; <input type="checkbox"/> Prototypes; <input type="checkbox"/> Software; <input type="checkbox"/> Products; <input type="checkbox"/> Services; <input type="checkbox"/> Collaborative platforms; <input type="checkbox"/> Data input; <input type="checkbox"/> Reports; <input type="checkbox"/> Educational material; <input type="checkbox"/> Policy recommendations; <input type="checkbox"/> Pre-standards;

<input type="checkbox"/> Protocols; <input type="checkbox"/> Processes/Frameworks; <input type="checkbox"/> Other – Please describe.
Section 2 – Target Groups
2.1 Which will be the main buyers you will be targeting.
2.2 Which will be the final end-users you this KER should target.
2.3 Which “unmet market need” this result will be addressed from those main buyers and final end-users.
2.4 Which other target groups are relevant for.
Section 3 – Exploitation Roadmap
3.1 Did this result/KER reach a level to be exploited or marketable? If not, which is the margin to improve to reach that level – what needs to be done.
3.2 How do you plan to exploit this KER?
<input type="checkbox"/> Use for further research; <input type="checkbox"/> Develop in-house and sell a new product/service; <input type="checkbox"/> Spin-off activity; <input type="checkbox"/> Open for Cooperation Agreement/Joint venture; <input type="checkbox"/> Sell IPR or IP-based business; <input type="checkbox"/> License IPR; <input type="checkbox"/> Transfer ownership of IPR to another partner from the consortium (identify who); <input type="checkbox"/> Standardisation activities on supporting current standards (specify which); <input type="checkbox"/> Standardisation activities on creating new standards (specify public info)
3.3 Which are the weaknesses (internal challenges) of your organisation to exploit this KER.
3.4 Which are the major strengths (internal assets) of your organisation to exploit this KER.
3.5 Do you foresee any potential exploitation risk(s) for this result? If so, besides a short description of it please provide classification of Likelihood (Low/Medium/High), Impact (Low/Medium/High), and Mitigations actions should be reported in a table.
3.6 Which specific SPINMATE activities until the end of the project will be done to scale up the result (specifying how much time is required in months)
3.7 Which partnerships are key to exploit this result

3.8 Do you hold all the background IP for exploiting this result. If not, which partner from SPINMATE share this knowledge with you and please include its contribution.
3.9 How do you plan to protect this new product/technology (KER)?
<input type="checkbox"/> Trade secret; <input type="checkbox"/> Copy right; <input type="checkbox"/> Trademark; <input type="checkbox"/> Patent; <input type="checkbox"/> Utility model; <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial design; <input type="checkbox"/> Other methods. Please indicate which: <input type="checkbox"/> No protection is foreseen. Please explain why:
Section 4 – WORKSHOP
Elaborate Business Plans in a collaborative session. Tool: <i>Business Model Canvas</i>
Annex 1: TRL 1 – basic principles observed TRL 2 – technology concept formulated TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept TRL 4 – technology validated in the laboratory TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in an operational environment TRL 8 – system complete and qualified TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)